

SEMANTIC AND THERAPEUTIC PROPERTIES OF LATIN PLANT NAMES

Karimova Asalkhan

*3rd year student of the Faculty of Pharmacy of Samarkand State Medical University,
Samarkand, Uzbekistan*

Abstract. This article discusses the Latin names of plants, their translation, natural medicinal properties, and their classification. It contains the dictionary meanings of semantic elements in Latin names of medicinal plants, Latin semantic classification of medicinal plants and therapeutic properties of plants.

Key words: sensory element, medicinal plant, semantic classification, therapeutic effect, pain, anatomical formation, chemical composition.

Latin names of medicinal plants are of considerable interest for study not only from a medical point of view, but also from a linguistic point of view. The linguistic composition of the Latin names of medicinal plants has a fair share of information content, which manifests itself upon closer examination of the lexical and morphological elements of plant names.

Thus, the names of plants may contain information not only about external characteristics (minor - small: *Vinca minor* - Small periwinkle; *pubescens* - fluffy: *Betula pubescens* - Fuzzy birch; *monogyna* - one-pistil: *Crataegus monogyna* - One-pistil hawthorn; *nigra* - black: *Sambucus nigra* - Black elder, etc.), but also about the therapeutic effect of plants, as well as about the biologically active substances they contain, which have different effects on the human body. It is this second category of names of medicinal plants that is the focus of our study.

The analysis of the lexical and morphological structure of the Latin names of medicinal plants can help to decipher the chemical structure of substances contained in plants and their medicinal properties. Thus, the purpose of the article is to identify the medicinal properties of plants by analyzing the lexical and morphological structure of the Latin names of medicinal plants. The objectives of the article, based on this goal, include:

- 1) to define the concept of "Latin names of medicinal plants";
- 2) to compile a classification of Latin names of medicinal plants in accordance with the lexical meanings of the names of the therapeutic effect of these plants;
- 3) to define the concept of "semantic element";
- 4) to compile a classification of semantic elements in the names of medicinal plants.

The material for the study was the Latin or Latinized names of medicinal plants. Researchers have noted the fact that in the last years of the 20th century, interest in the use of medicinal plants has increased among both medical workers and the population. And this is understandable: a third of medicines are prepared from plant materials; folk traditions of phytotherapy, valuable information about medicinal herbs are increasingly covered in the literature [2,4].

The popularity of using medicinal plants has also increased due to the fact that medicinal plants have a number of advantages that synthetic drugs may not have. For example, biologically active substances obtained synthetically are very often inferior to their natural analogues in pharmacological effect. In this case, the advantage remains with the "living laboratory", that is, with the plant [1,9].

Another advantage of medicinal plants is their low toxicity, complex effect and the possibility of long-term use without significant side effects. In addition, excessive use of synthetic drugs has led to the so-called "drug disease" - complications resulting from uncontrolled use of synthetic drugs,

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

allergic reactions. In connection with the ever-increasing popularity of medicinal plants among the population, a clear knowledge of not only Russian, but also Latin names of medicinal plants, as well as their therapeutic effects, is becoming more relevant and necessary for future specialists.

The benefits of studying the relationship between the meanings of Latin names of medicinal plants and their therapeutic effect can also include the relationship between the meanings of Latin names of medicinal plants and various branches of medical science - pharmaceutics (since the Latin names of medicinal plants can reflect their chemical composition), anatomy (since the Latin name of a medicinal plant can indicate the attribution of its therapeutic effect to a specific anatomical formation), clinical science (the Latin name of a medicinal plant can indicate the attribution of its effect to a specific disease or symptoms).

The novelty of the undertaken research is in the systematization of Latin names of medicinal plants in accordance with the lexical meanings of the semantic elements included in their structure and the therapeutic effect of plants. Latin names of medicinal plants are the names or designations of plants with medicinal properties, containing in their lexical and morphological structure Latin or Latinized (for example, Greek), that is, borrowed by the Latin language, elements - roots, prefixes, suffixes, endings - and reflecting certain characteristics of the plant: external characteristics (color, shape, size, tactile properties), medicinal properties of plants, characteristics of their chemical composition. Sometimes Latin names of medicinal plants contain the names of researchers, scientists who first described their properties, mythological characters.

Semantic classification of Latin names of medicinal plants subdivides these names in accordance with their lexical meaning or the lexical meaning of the elements that make them up - prefixes, roots, suffixes. The part of the name of a medicinal plant that has an independent lexical meaning is called a semantic element.

For example, the name *Erythraea centaurium* (small centaur) contains three semantic elements:

1) "erythr-" from the Greek "erythros" - "red", hence the connection of the semantic element in the name with the term "erythrocytes" (red blood cells) and, consequently, with the medical use of the plant for a blood disease - anemia (a decrease in the number of red blood cells);

2) "cent-" from the Latin "centum" - "one hundred; a lot" [5, 12];

3) "aur-" from the Latin "aurum, i n" - "gold; golden color" [17], which is associated with both the chemical composition of the plant (flavonoid content - from Latin flavus, a, um - golden, yellow [5:457]), and its medical use (for jaundice, scrofula) [21,24].

The name *Erythroxyllum* has two semantic elements:

1) "erythr-" from the Greek "erythros" - "red";

2) "-oxy-" from the Greek "oxys" - "sour", or from the Latin "Oxygenium, i n" - "oxygen", which indicates the connection with the use of the plant in hypoxia - oxygen starvation.

Sometimes the semantic element can be the entire word in the name: minor - small in *Vinca minor* (Small periwinkle).

In accordance with the lexical meanings of the semantic elements of the Latin names of medicinal plants, the names are divided into:

1. Names that include semantic elements that are related to the names of diseases or symptoms of certain diseases for which these plants are used:

Tussilago, inis f – Coltsfoot: here we see the semantic element "tussi-" related to the Latin words "tussis, is f" - "cough" (symptom), "tussio, ire" - "to cough" [9,14]; "pertussis, is f" - "whooping

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

cough" (disease), which suggests to us information about the medical use of tussilago as a means of facilitating coughing, especially for whooping cough, thinning sputum [26]; Scrophularia, ae f – Figwort: the semantic element "scrophul-" comes from the Latin "scrofula, ae f" – "enlargement of the lymph glands; scrofula", hence the name of the disease "scrophulosis" (scrofulosis) → the raw material of the plant is used for tuberculosis of the lymph nodes of the neck, festering wounds, ulcers, skin diseases [10]; Rheum, i n – Rhubarb: the semantic element "rheu-" comes from the Greek "rheo" – "flow" → "rrhoea" – "flow, outflow", which is included in the names of such diseases as "diarrhoea" – "diarrhea", "haemorrhoea" – "hemorrhoids" → the use of the plant for pathogenetic fluid leakage from the body – for diarrhea (as an astringent), hemorrhoids [13].

2. Names that include semantic elements that reflect the therapeutic effect of medicinal plants:

Tussilago, inis f – Coltsfoot: the final semantic element "-ago" from the Latin "ago, ere" - "to set in motion, to drive; to move [6,17]; to pursue" → literally "Tussilago" - "I drive away the cough" → "-ago" in the Latin name of the medicinal plant means "removal of symptoms or causes of the disease"; Plumbago, inis f – Leadwort: the semantic elements "plumb-" from "Plumbum, i n" - "Lead" [20] and "-ago" from "ago, ere" - "to drive, to pursue" [27,30] → literally: "I drive away Lead": used as an antidote for lead poisoning, as an emetic, freeing the stomach from toxic substances that have entered it; Pulsatilla, ae f – Pasqueflower / Pulsatilla: the semantic element "puls-/pulsati-" from the Latin "pulsare" - "to move, to induce, to disturb"; "pulsatio, onis f" - "pushing, beating, blow"; «pulsus, us m» - «push, incentive» [18,25] → preparations based on pulsus stimulate the immune and hormonal systems; recommended for impotence, nervous exhaustion accompanied by lethargy, depression, motor retardation [13]; about diseases, physiological problems, chemical composition: «lith-o-sperm-» consists of two s.e.; the first s.e. «lith-» in the name of the plant speaks of its use in diseases associated with stones (← Greek «lithos» - «stone») - in urolithiasis, cholelithiasis; the second s.e. «-sperm-» (← lat. «sperma, ae f» - «seed») speaks of the influence of the medicinal raw material of the plant on the functions of the sex glands, is used for problems with ejaculation, etc.; the combination of both elements in the name of the plant speaks of the presence in its composition of lithospermic acid, which blocks the action of gonadotropic hormones responsible for the functions of the sex glands; about the directly opposite therapeutic effect, but related to one area of the human body: se.e. «rheu-» (in «Rheum» - «Rhubarb») and «rhoeo-» (in «Rhoeo» - «Reo») in accordance with its meaning - «to flow; flow" - they say that plants help to eliminate disturbances in the correct flow of fluids in the body, but their therapeutic effect can extend to directly opposite (antonymous) diseases: depending on the dosage, rhubarb (Rheum) can be used both as a laxative and for diarrhea (diarrhoea); also, rheo (Rhoeo) can increase the excretion of fluid from the body (as a diuretic), or, on the contrary, stop it (as a hemostatic).

The study of the Latin names of medicinal plants not only helps to decipher their medicinal properties based on the semantic elements included in the names, denoting certain diseases, anatomical formations or features of the chemical composition, but also promotes the development of associative thinking (the meaning or sound-letter filling of a particular semantic element in the name evokes a whole series of associations, ideas: "rheu-" / "rhoeo-" is associated in the mind with the Greek "rheo" - "to flow, current", with the term "rrhoea", included in the names of diseases such as diarrhea, hemorrhoids, etc.).

1) Working on the lexical meaning of a particular semantic element of the Latin name of a plant in relation to its therapeutic effect, one can form a clearer and deeper understanding of the nature of a particular disease (for example, the observation of the word erythr- in the names of plants allows us to

again associate it with red blood cells, and therefore with blood, and to clarify the nature of such diseases as anemia - a decrease in the number of red blood cells, or hypoxia, also associated with red blood cells - oxygen carriers in the body);

2) A particular element included in the chemical composition of the plant (thus, the se-e.g. aur- helps to find lexical associations of the adjectives aureus, a, um - golden and flavus, a, um - fiery yellow, golden, yellow, an in-depth analysis of the term "flavonoids", clarification of the chemical composition of flavonoids and their therapeutic effect);

3) The functions, structure of certain anatomical structures and organs (thus, the se-e.g. carneum - fleshy evokes an association with the anatomical formation trabeculae carneae - fleshy trabeculae, which are one of the important components of the heart, and hence the conclusion suggests itself about the therapeutic effect of the plant, the name of which includes the element carneum (Sedum carneum), on the heart and diseases associated with it).

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. «Артерии и вены под защитой лекарственных растений» // «АиФ. Здоровье» №28 14/07/2005 [электронный ресурс]. URL: www.aif.ru
2. Брезгин Н. Н. Лекарственные растения Верхневолжья. Ярославль, Верх.-Волж. кн.изд., 1973. 224 с.
3. «Вена – с русского на греческий» [электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://translate.academic.ru>
4. Мифы народов мира: энциклопедия в двух томах. М.: «Советская энциклопедия», 1988.
5. Латинско-русский словарь / Авт.-сост. К. А. Тананушко. – Минск: ООО «Харвест», 2008. – 1344 с.
6. Лавренова Г. В., Лавренов В. К. Энциклопедия лекарственных растений. Том 1. – Изд-во «Донецчина», 1997 [электронный ресурс]. URL: <https://litlife.club>
7. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). Studies of Reciprocity in Linguistics. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 8, 221-224.
8. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). The role of teaching latin in the course of subject training of future foreign language teachers. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 11-14.
9. Makhmudov, Z. M., & Sharipov, B. S. LOTIN TILI VA TIBBIY TERMINOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISHNING DIDAKTIK TAMOYILLARI VA UNING ASOSI HAQIDA FIKRLAR.
10. Mardanovich, M. Z., Aliaskarovna, S. U., Kenjaevna, B. M., Genjebaevna, A. P., & Salimovich, S. B. (2021). Some Considerations about Legal Solutions and Practices of Certain Problems Writing Recipes. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 5341-5352.
11. Mukhamadiyeva, M., & Sharipov, B. (2022). LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(7), 337-339.
12. ZAFAR, M., BOBUR, S., & DILMUROD, B. R. (2021). Scientific and pedagogical basis of teaching the theory of decisions in school chemistry. *International Journal of Philosophical Studies and Social Sciences*, 1(3), 192-196.
13. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Developing Students Attitudes Towards the Environment When Teaching a Foreign Languages. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 1(1), 199-201.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

14. Шарипов, Б. С. (2022). TIL BIRLIKLARINING NUTQDA FAOLLASHUVI HAQIDA. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(1).
15. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Influence of the latin language on the formation of medical terminology. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 16-20.
16. Sharipov, B., Makhmudov, Z., & Buriyev, D. (2023). Features of teaching latin to students medical universities studying in english. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(1), 21-25.
17. Makhmudov, Z., Sharipov, B., & Bo'riyev, D. (2023). Tibbiyot universitetlarida lotin tili va tibbiy terminologiya fanini o'qitishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(1), 5-10.
18. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Modern Methods of Teaching Latin and Medical Terminology in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(5), 190-192.
19. Mardanovich, M. Z., Salimovich, S. B., & Arzimurodovich, B. D. (2021). Reviews of effective use of educational methods in teaching latin and medical terminology. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 381-386.
20. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
21. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.
22. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.
23. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).
24. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).
25. Nasimjanovna, K. F., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 469-474.
26. Isroilova, M., & Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME OBSERVATIONS ON LATIN PRONUNCIATION AND SPELLING. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 2(7), 127-129.
27. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.
28. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). TRANSLATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND BASIC MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY CLASSES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 100-103.

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-8

29. Махмудов, З. М., & Шарипов, Б. С. Талабаларнинг фанни яхши ўрганишлари учун психо-эмоционал таъсир этишда халқ мақол ва маталларидан тўғри фойдаланиш (лотин тили ва тиббий терминология фани мисолида). *Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych*, 112.
30. Bektosheva, E. D., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). LATIN AND GREC TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF STUDY OF OPERATIVE SURGERY. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(6), 66-72.
31. Sharipov Bobur Salimovich. (2023). ESSENTIAL COMMENTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO THE ORIGIN OF CLINICAL TERMS AND FEATURES OF CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(6), 144–148. Retrieved from <https://refocus.uz/index.php/1/article/view/296>
32. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). SOME THOUGHTS ON THE IMPORTANCE AND HISTORY OF THE LATIN LANGUAGE IN WORLD LANGUAGES. *Research Focus*, 2(10), 49-53.
33. Mardanovich, M. Z., & Salimovich, S. B. Auditoriyadan tashqari ta'lim-tarbiyaga maqsadli, tizimli yondashish. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 455).
34. Salimovich, S. B. (2024). USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY OF A DOCTOR (BASED ON THE MATERIAL OF AN OUTPATIENT'S MEDICAL CARD). *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(1), 276-281.
35. Asalkhan, K., & Salimovich, S. B. (2024). GINGER-BENEFITS AND HARMFUL PROPERTIES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 86-91.
36. Asalkhan, K., & Salimovich, S. B. (2024). O'SIMLIK XOM ASHYOSIDAN OLINADIGAN DORI VOSITALARINING TIBBIYOTDA ISHLATILISHI VA XUSUSIYATLARI. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(2), 102-111
37. . SHARIPOV, B. RETSIPOKLIK TUZILISHI VA UNING GRAMMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI TO 'G 'RISIDA AYRIM MULOHAZALAR. *Я ПРЕПОДАВАНИЕ*, 173.
38. Salimovich, S. B. (2024). ANATOMICAL, PHARMACEUTICAL AND CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY IN LATIN CLASSES. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(1), 483-495.